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Improved Assessment and Mapping of the Riverine Hydrokinetic Resource in the Continental United States

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Abstract

The US Department of Energy's national river hydrokinetic resource assessment for the United States, conducted over ten years ago, estimated a theoretical potential hydrokinetic energy resource of 1300 TWh/yr and a technical resource of 99 TWh/yr. The goal of the present study is to reassess these resources with improved data sources and methodologies, including an analysis of the interannual and seasonal variability of the estimates, at the top 20 locations for each of the 18 hydrographic regions in the CONUS. Hourly discharge and stream velocity from the National Water Model Retrospective v2.1 dataset, a 42-year retrospective simulation including over 2.7 million river reaches, are incorporated to estimate the distribution of theoretical and technical resource across the range of flows at all locations. The technically recoverable resource is directly computed using the range of flow statistics for each river segment with estimated channel shape and an assumed array deployment. These methodologies, their validation and preliminary results are presented. Once completed, the magnitude and geographical distribution of the theoretical and technical river hydrokinetic resource for the United States can be disseminated as part of the USDOE's marine energy atlas to support regional energy planning and river hydrokinetic project siting and development.

Keywords: river; hydrokinetic; resource assessment; CONUS

1. Introduction

The US Department of Energy's national river hydrokinetic resource assessment for the United States, conducted over ten years ago, estimated a theoretical potential hydrokinetic energy resource of 1300 TWh/yr and a technical resource of 99 TWh/yr [1]. This resource assessment used the hydrologic model hindcast, NHDPlusV1, and the National Elevation Dataset (NED) [2], which at the time were the best available data sources for key input parameters, including average annual discharge and elevation change. A review of this hydrokinetic resource assessment by the National Academy of Sciences found the methodology and estimates of the theoretical resource to be acceptable, but not for the technically recoverable resource due to inherent assumptions within the methodology for not incorporating the statistical spatial distribution and temporal variation of stream flow and indirectly estimating the resource using the recovery factor approach [3]. The goal of the present study is to reassess the riverine hydrokinetic energy resource

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in the CONUS using the hydrologic model hindcast product developed by NOAA, the National Water Model Retrospective V2.1(NWMv2.1) dataset [4], which uses more up-to-date NED, while also providing higher temporal resolution data, e.g., hourly discharge and flow velocity data that can be used to characterize and assess the inter-annual and seasonal variability of the resource; and the improved methodology for the technical resource.

2. Methodology

2.1. Dataset

Hourly flowrate and stream velocity between January 1, 1980 and December 31, 2020 are retrieved from the National Water Model Retrospective V2.1(NWMv2.1) dataset, a 42-year retrospective simulation including over 2.7 million river reaches. The NWMv2.1 has a number of improvements compared to NHDPlusV1. The NHDPlusV1 has fewer flowlines than NWMv2.1 and NHDPlusV1 provides a single mean flowrate from historical values for each flowline. Also, NWMv2.1 uses an improved 10-m NED as data input, which is updated from the 2004 version of the 30-m NED for NHDPlusV1 [5]. The flowline attributes for each river reach necessary to estimate the power are retrieved from NHDPlusV2 available at [6]. The hydrographic regions from [1] shown in Figure 1 is adopted to divide the CONUS into 18 regions for which the theoretical and technical power is calculated.

The top 20 stream segments with the mean average flowrate for each hydrographic region are selected as initial study locations prior to extending the study domain to a full dataset. Although this estimation does not give a complete assessment of the riverine hydrokinetic resource in the CONUS, it enables the investigation of the natural variability that is present in the hydrokinetic resource. Any flowline that overlaps with dams are removed from consideration. For identifying potential REC sites, it is assumed that the turbines are in a state of consistent operation in steady flow, subcritical flow [7].

Figure 1. 18 Hydrographic regions for which the power is calculated in the CONUS

2.2. Theoretical power computation

The theoretical resource is defined as the gross amount of power that can be harnessed from running water based on the conversion from gravitational potential energy to kinetic energy that occurs within a reach [1]. The theoretical power is calculated using the equation

$$P_{th} = \gamma Q \Delta H \cdot 10^{-9} \quad (1)$$

where P_{th} is the theoretical power (GW), γ is the specific weight of water ($\sim 9800 \text{ N/m}^3$), Q is the flowrate (m^3/s), and ΔH is the change in elevation over the length of the segment (m). The unit is converted to GW by multiplying 10^{-9} . This equation is also used to calculate the theoretical power in [1].

2.3. Technical power computation

The technical resource considers selected technological constraints and efficiency associated with turbines, resulting in a more accurate representation of the potential power that can be generated from deployment by considering the energy lost in the process of capture and conversion [1]. The technically recoverable power is computed using the equation

$$P_{tech} = \frac{\rho}{2} \xi N A_r V_t^3 \cdot 10^{-9} \quad (2)$$

where P_{tech} is the technical power (GW), ξ is the device efficiency, N is the number of devices, A_r is the swept area of a device (m^2), and V_t is the flow velocity with devices present (m/s). The number of devices is determined using the “rule of thumb” spacing in [1], which assumes that devices would be distributed uniformly over the channel bottom in rows. The longitudinal spacing between rows of devices is $8.66V^{-0.086}D$ [8], which allows for flow velocity to significantly recover from wake dissipation, and devices are separated by $2D$ in each row. D is the device diameter, which is assumed to be 80% of the 5-percentile flow. This initial estimation considers the minimum thresholds on velocity and water depth of 0.5 m/s and 2 m respectively. The average width of a river segment is estimated using the global-averaged width-discharge equation [9]

$$w = 7.2Q^{0.50} \quad (3)$$

where w is the width (m) and Q is the flowrate (m^3/s). Equation (3) is adopted by [10, 11] respectively to perform the global river resource assessment and to estimate the width of flowlines at mean annual discharge in North America. Device deployment in a channel induces a rise in water level and decrease in flow velocity referred to as “backwater effect”. The water depth attributed to deploying turbines can be found by solving the following equations [1, 12]:

$$h_t = h \cdot \left(b - \frac{0.245}{b} + 0.0994 \right) \quad (4.1)$$

$$b = \left[0.4766 \cdot a + \{ (0.4766 \cdot a + 0.69555)^2 + 0.01466 \}^{1/2} + 0.69555 \right]^{1/3} \quad (4.2)$$

$$a = \left(\frac{3}{4} \frac{\xi(1+\epsilon)}{n^2 g} \cdot \frac{N A_r}{wL} \right) \cdot h^{1/3} \quad (4.3)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\left(\frac{w}{2D} \right) A_r}{w h_t} \quad (4.4)$$

where h_t is the water depth with devices present (m), h is the water depth (m), ϵ is the blockage ratio, n is Manning’s roughness coefficient, g is the gravitational acceleration (~ 9.81 m/s²), and L is the channel length (m). The average cross-sectional area of a channel (A), water depth (h), and Manning’s roughness coefficient (n) can be estimated assuming a rectangular channel cross-section and no flow beyond the bankfull. Finally, the flow velocity with device present can be found using the continuity

$$V_t = \left(\frac{h}{h_t} \right)^{5/3} V \quad (5)$$

where V_t is the velocity with devices present (m/s), h is the water depth (m), h_t is the water depth with devices present (m), and V is the water depth (m/s).

2.4. Annual energy production

The annual energy production (AEP) is estimated by

$$AEP = \frac{1}{41} \sum P \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (6)$$

where $\sum P$ is the sum of hourly theoretical or technical power between 1980 and 2020, and the value is converted from GWh/yr to TWh/yr by multiplying 10^{-3} .

3. Results

3.1. AEP comparison between revised and EPRI 2012 report

Based on the results from the top 20 stream segments at each of the 18 hydrographic regions, the theoretical and technical AEP estimates using the improved data and methodology are compared to those obtained following the methodology in [1] are shown in Table 1. Overall, the total theoretical estimates decreased from 31.67 TWh/yr to 29.36 TWh/yr, whereas the total technical estimates increased from 7.05 TWh/yr to 9.90 TWh/yr. The difference is mostly attributed to Lower Mississippi while increase or decrease is also observed in other regions.

Table 1. Theoretical and technical AEP for the top 20 locations at each hydrographic region using the revised and EPRI methodology. The percent differences for the theoretical and technical has been calculated with the revised values as the baseline

Hydrographic region	Revised Theoretical (TWh/yr)	EPRI Theoretical (TWh/yr)	% Difference Theoretical	Revised Technical (TWh/yr)	EPRI Technical (TWh/yr)	% Difference Technical
1. Northeast	0.13	0.14	+7.7	0.02	0.00	-
2. Mid-Atlantic	0.17	0.10	-41.2	0.05	0.01	-80.0
3. South Atlantic	0.91	1.33	+46.2	0.08	0.07	-12.5
4. Great Lakes	0.08	0.05	-37.5	0.01	0.00	-
5. Ohio	0.30	1.28	+326.7	0.06	0.21	+250.0
6. Tennessee	0.03	0.06	+100.0	0.00	0.00	-
7. Upper Mississippi	2.51	1.20	-52.2	1.07	0.22	-79.4
8. Lower Mississippi	17.44	19.68	+12.8	6.49	5.74	-11.6
9. Souris-Red-Rainv	0.10	0.04	-60.0	0.00	0.00	-
10. Missouri	2.17	1.37	-36.9	0.85	0.17	-80.0
11. Ark-Red-White	0.79	0.78	-1.3	0.27	0.08	-70.4
12. Texas	0.21	0.15	-28.6	0.02	0.00	-
13. Rio Grande	0.77	0.46	-40.3	0.05	0.01	-80.0
14. Upper Colorado	0.35	0.44	+25.7	0.01	0.01	-
15. Lower Colorado	0.72	1.01	+40.3	0.19	0.10	-47.4
16. Great Basin	0.26	0.16	-38.5	0.00	0.00	-
17. Pacific Northwest	1.44	2.34	+62.5	0.63	0.40	-36.5
18. California	0.98	1.08	+10.2	0.10	0.03	-70.0
TOTAL	29.36	31.67	+8.3	9.90	7.05	-28.8

3.2. Interannual and monthly variability of technical AEP

The interannual variabilities of technical AEP for the 1980-2020 period and the monthly variabilities of that for an average year are measured using the 95% confidence interval (CI) and the coefficient of variation (COV). For the interannual variabilities, Lower Mississippi has the largest 95% CI with 6.49 ± 0.57 TWh/yr and the COV of the region is 0.27. Upper Colorado has the 95% CI of 0.01 ± 0.004 TWh/yr and the largest COV of 1.17. This tells us that the absolute variation of the technical AEP is the largest in Lower Mississippi, and the relative variation of that is the largest in Upper Colorado. For the monthly variabilities, Great Basin has the largest COV with 1.65 followed by Upper Colorado with 1.53, and Lower Colorado had the lowest COV with 0.16. The large seasonality in technical AEP at the two regions may be attributed to freezing and melting of ice before and after winter.

The interannual trend of technical AEP during the 1980-2020 period for selected hydrographic regions with technical AEP above 1TWh/yr are shown in Figure 3a. Lower Mississippi, Upper Mississippi, and Missouri have increased technical AEP in recent years, which indicates that the regions have become wetter with increase in streamflow. The seasonal trend of technical AEP within an average year are shown for the selected hydrographic regions in Figure 3b. Lower Mississippi, Upper Mississippi, Missouri, and Pacific Northwest shows increased AEP during late spring and summer months while decreased AEP during fall and early winter. South Atlantic and California peaks in late winter through early spring and drops in summer and fall.

Figure 2. (a) Interannual and (b) average monthly technical AEP for selected hydrographic regions

4. Conclusions

NOAA's hydrologic model hindcast data product, the NWM, which has improved aspects from the previous hindcast data product, NHDPlusV1, enables a more accurate assessment and mapping of the riverine hydrokinetic resource in the CONUS. Its higher temporal resolution enables characterization and assessment of the inter-annual and seasonal variability of the hydrokinetic resource and an improved methodology for estimating the technical resource that addresses flaws identified by the National Academy of Sciences in the previous technical resource assessment.

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